

OpenMod Africa

Specifications of the extensions of the open-source models

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List of Abbreviations

AFREC	African Energy Commission
AFREP	African Renewable Energy Profiles
APM	Average Participation Method
CAPEX	CAPital Expenditure
CEM	Capacity Expansion Model
CLMS	Copernicus Land Monitoring System
CMP	African Continental power systems Master Plan
CSV	Comma Separated Values
DC	Direct Current
EAC	East African Community
EAPP	Eastern African Power Pool
ECOWAS	Economic Community Of Western African States
ECREEE	ECOWAS Centre for Renewable Energy and Energy Efficiency
ESS	Energy Storage System
EU	European Union
EV	Electric Vehicle
GDP	Gross Domestic Product
GIS	Geographic Information System
HV	High Voltage
IEA	International Energy Agency
IPCC	Intergovernmental Panel for Climate Change
LCOE	Levelized Cost Of Electricity
MV	Medium Voltage
NECP	National Energy and Climate Plan
NTC	Net Transfer Capacity
OM4A	Open Modelling toolbox For Africa
OPEX	OPERating EXpenditure

POI	Point Of Interest
PTDF	Power Transfer Distribution Factor
PV	PhotoVoltaic
RE&EE	Renewable Energy & Energy Efficiency
RES	Renewable Energy System
SSV	Seasonal Storage Valuation
TSO	Transmission System Operator
UC	Unit Commitment
UMOA / WAMU	Union Monétaire Ouest Africaine / West African Monetary Union
WAPP	Western African Power Pool

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Executive Summary

The Horizon Europe Energy project 101118123 – OpenMod4Africa (Open Modelling Toolbox for development of long-term pathways for the energy system in Africa) is a three-year project (2023–2026) about the development of an energy modelling toolbox for analyses of the future energy and power systems in Africa. Furthermore, capacity building in the use of models and further development of the toolbox, among African experts, is a core element in the project.

The main objective is to contribute to an improved and robust understanding of how to develop an energy and a power supply to all Africans by making available, demonstrating and using an open modelling Toolbox. The OM4A Toolbox will be populated with a suite of open integrated state-of-the-art models and a common database including all necessary data for conducting among other scenario building exercises at regional, national and pan-African level. Two case studies are demonstrating the use of the Toolbox, and in addition providing new insights into important challenges related to the energy transition. The research in the project is done in dialogue with two stakeholder groups, one in the Eastern African Power Pool region and one in the Western African Power Pool region.

In this deliverable we focus on the necessary extensions of the models functionalities to make them relevant for conducting energy system transition studies in Africa.

The OM4A Toolbox includes the 6 following models:

- GEnesYS-MOD which analyzes long-term low-carbon energy transition pathways considering all energy sectors: electricity, buildings, industry, and transport;
- openTEPES, a decision support system for defining the integrated generation, storage, and transmission expansion plan of a large-scale electric systems;
- plan4res, a power system model, which includes capacity expansion module (adaptation of the generation and storage mix as well as of the existing interconnections of a given year), focused on the optimization of the strategies for managing seasonal storages, and the simulation of the system operation. plan4res focuses on electricity;
- InfraFair which determines the network utilisation by agents (demand and generators using the network) and countries;
- OnSSET, a Geographic Information Systems (GIS) based tool that enhances electrification planning and decision-making for the accomplishment of energy access goals in currently unserved areas;
- EV-PV, whose goal is to support planning and decision-making for the deployment of charging stations for electric vehicles (EVs).

The current models functionalities have been analysed in regard to the openMod4Africa case studies specifications. The following extensions will allow the studies to be conducted as smoothly as possible:

- The mathematical modelling is sufficient to represent the required characteristics of the African energy systems. Thus, no extension to this mathematical modelling, nor the linked solving algorithm, is necessary.

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- GENeSYS-MOD, openTEPES and plan4res will not require any extension related to the mathematical modelling or the solving algorithms. However, the technological scope of the models needs to be extended regarding the demand side (to include different demand sectors, in particular cooking) as well as for the network modelling (to include the offgrid demand). These extensions will be conducted via evolutions of the data workflow.
 - InfraFair and OnSSEt have been developed and used within an African context and, thus, do not require adaptation.
 - EV-PV extensions will focus on the following extensions:
 - Including more passenger transport modes (Private transport: add motorbikes, public transport: minibus taxi, regular buses, rapid transit buses)
 - The methodology applied to determine the PV potential will be adapted to the local context.

This document also includes recommendations for the modelling teams regarding the documentation (for installation and use), and the design and development of the linkage scripts (which allow soft-linkage of the models via data sharing, based on a common format and nomenclature, as well as the use of the scenario explorer).

1 Introduction

The Horizon Europe Energy project 101118123 – OpenMod4Africa (Open Modelling Toolbox for development of long-term pathways for the energy system in Africa) is a three-year project (2023–2026) about development of an energy modelling toolbox for analyses of the future energy and power systems in Africa. Furthermore, capacity building among African experts in use and development of the toolbox is a core element in the project.

The main objective is to contribute to an improved and robust understanding of how to develop an energy and a power supply to all Africans by making available, demonstrating and using an open modelling Toolbox. The Toolbox will be populated with a suite of open integrated state-of-the-art models and a common database including all necessary data for conducting among other scenario building exercises at regional, national and pan-African level. Two case studies are demonstrating the use of the Toolbox, and in addition providing new insight into important challenges related to the energy transition. The research in the project is done in dialogue with two stakeholder groups, one in the Eastern African Power Pool region and one in the Western African Power Pool region.

The overall objective of WP3, ‘Model development and adaptation’ is expanding the functionalities and adapting the features of the models within the Toolbox developed in WP4, so that they are able to adequately represent the transition of the energy systems in Africa towards sustainable ones. The specific objectives to be pursued related to the former are listed next:

1. Design and implementation of the integration of additional open-source models into the Toolbox.
2. Development of detailed specifications of the upgrades that the models should undergo.
3. Implementation of the upgrades to the models previously specified.

This deliverable aims at completing Objective 2, via Task 3.2 ‘Detailed specification of the extensions of open-source models’.

The main body of this document is composed of three chapters:

- In chapter 2 we introduce the 6 models which are part of the OM4A Toolbox:
 - GEnesYS-MOD which analyzes long-term low-carbon energy transition pathways considering all energy sectors: electricity, buildings, industry, and transport;
 - openTEPES, a decision support system for defining the integrated generation, storage, and transmission expansion plan of a large-scale electric system;
 - plan4res, a power system model, which includes capacity expansion (adaptation of the generation and storage mix as well as of the existing interconnections of a given year), optimization of the strategies for managing seasonal storages, and simulation of the system operation. plan4res focuses on electricity;
 - InfraFair which determines the network utilisation by agents (demand and generators using the network) and countries;
 - OnSSET, a Geographic Information Systems (GIS) based tool that enhances electrification planning and decision-making for the accomplishment of energy access goals in currently unserved areas;
 - EV-PV, whose goal of EV-PV is to support planning and decision-making for the deployment of charging stations for electric vehicles (EVs).

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- In chapter 3 we define the extensions which are necessary for adaptation to the African context.
 - Chapter 4 focuses on the adaptations of models concerning their IT requirements. The aspects touched upon here include the following:
 - What is required to make the installation and use of the models easier?
 - What could be a good workflow for the case studies within openMod4Africa, ie. How to link the different models in a consistent way.

2 Summary of models in the OM4A Toolbox

2.1 GENeSYS-MOD

The Global Energy System Model (GENeSYS-MOD) is a linear open-source energy system model which is tailored to analyze long-term low-carbon energy transition pathways considering all energy sectors: electricity, buildings, industry, and transport. First published by Löffler et al. (2017), it extends the Open Source Energy Modelling System (OSeMOSYS) framework and, since then, it has been expanded to include numerous additional features and functionalities. Its main strength lies in its ability to simultaneously optimize the capacity expansion, energy generation, and dispatch of the system for all the main energy sectors, which leads to an endogenous optimization of the entire energy system. This then also takes into account the additional electricity demand from sector coupling by considering interactions between all energy sectors, as well as storage, grid, and other flexibility requirements.

The main Inputs and Outputs of GENeSYS-MOD are the following:

Main Inputs:

- Baseline demand data (final energy per uses)
- Renewable potential
- Cost assumptions (investment and operation costs per technology)
- Weather data
- Installed capacities and grid at the starting year
- Political targets (carbon price and/or emissions)

Main Outputs:

- Primary energy demand (per fuel)
- Sectoral demands
- Technology investments
- Costs
- Renewable generation
- Fossil fuel phase-out planned schedules
- CO2 emissions

2.2 OpenTEPES

The OpenTEPES model is a decision support system for defining the integrated generation, storage, and transmission expansion plan of a large-scale electric system at a tactical level¹. The user pre-defines the expansion candidates, so that the model determines the optimal decisions among those specified by the user as possible. Essentially, any power related technology focused on generation and storage can be considered by this tool, including the conventional generation units (thermal -nuclear, gas, coal), energy storage of different types (hydro, pumped-hydro, battery, electric vehicle, demand response, alkaline water electrolyzer, solar thermal) and variable renewable (onshore and offshore wind power, solar PV, run-of-the-river). Besides, the representation of the hydro system based on volume and water inflow data considers the water stream topology (hydro cascade basins).

The main Inputs and Outputs of OpenTEPES are the following:

Main Inputs:

- Electricity demand: hourly electricity demand or hourly profiles and annual electricity demand
- Interconnections features: characteristics of (existing) transmission lines between regions (capacity, capital cost, reactance and loss factor)
- Generation technologies: both conventional and variable RES
- Thermal generation: capacity, variable cost, dynamic constraints for each individual plant
- Hydro power (separated into hydro with reservoir, pumped storage and run of river): capacity, efficiency of pumping, volume, inflows, variable cost, seasonality (daily, weekly, monthly, etc)
- Wind Power and Solar PV (PhotoVoltaic): capacity, variable cost and hourly profiles

Main Outputs:

- Investment: generation, storage, hydro reservoirs, electric lines and hydrogen pipelines investment decisions and associated costs
- Operation: unit commitment, startup, and shutdown of non-renewable units, unit output and aggregation by technologies (thermal, storage hydro, pumped-hydro storage, RES -Renewable energy Sources-), RES curtailment, electric line and hydrogen pipeline flows, line ohmic losses, node voltage angles, upward and downward operating reserves, ESS (Energy Storage System) inventory levels, hydro reservoir volumes, power and hydrogen not served
- Emissions: CO2 emissions by unit
- Marginal values: locational Short-Run Marginal Costs, stored energy value, water volume value
- Economic: operation, emission, and reliability costs and revenues from operation and operating reserves
- Flexibility: flexibility provided by demand, for the different generation and consumption technologies, and for power not served

¹ Tactical planning is concerned with time horizons of 10-20 years

2.3 plan4res

plan4res is a power system model, which includes capacity expansion (adaptation of the generation and storage mix as well as of the existing interconnections of a given year), optimization of the strategies for managing seasonal storages, and simulation of the system operation. plan4res focuses on electricity. It includes all power generation technologies, electricity storage technologies, and a (usually aggregated) representation of the interconnections between regions (the transmission grid within one region is not represented, nevertheless, the granularity of regions can be adapted to the modelling needs).

The main Inputs and Outputs of plan4res are the following:

Main Inputs:

- Electricity demand: hourly electricity demand or hourly profiles and annual electricity demand
- System services requirements: primary and secondary reserve (if relevant), Inertia requirements
- Interconnections: characteristics of (existing) transmission lines between regions: capacity, investment cost, impedance (if needed)
- Generation mix:
 - Thermal generation (fossil, nuclear, biomass plants): installed capacity, availability schedules and any other restriction, variable and capital costs, system services capacity, dynamic constraints if the user wishes to represent plants individually
 - Hydro power, including seasonal storage (reservoirs with large capacity, which are managed in general over one year), (short term) storage: this relates to small reservoirs, managed over 1 week or 1 day and run of river: installed capacity, volumes of reservoirs (if any), pumping efficiency, inflows, system services capacities, costs (for short term storage)
 - Variable renewable generation (other than hydro), mainly windpower and PV: installed capacity, system services capacities (if relevant), costs, hourly profiles which, applied to the capacity, give the hourly maximum power, depending on meteorological conditions (can be scenarized)
 - (short term) storage (apart from hydro): installed capacity, volume of the storage, charging / discharging efficiencies, inflows or independent demand (e.g. for EV -Electric Vehicle- storage), costs

Main Outputs:

- Investment decisions: generation, storage, interconnections
- Power generation schedules
- System services mobilisation schedules
- Inertia procurement schedules
- Volume of reservoirs
- Marginal costs of electricity
- Marginal costs of system services and of interconnections
- Flows between regions

2.4 InfraFair

The InfraFair model determines the network utilisation by agents (demand and generators using the network) and countries. Based on this utilisation and assuming that it reflects the economic benefits received by agents, it determines the responsibility of each agent in the construction of each element in the network. In order to reasonably reflect the stakeholder's utilisation of network infrastructure, multiple representative snapshots of the annual network usage should be provided. InfraFair is a decision support tool for network cost allocation and tariff design for regional power transmission infrastructure, but it can be used for national infrastructure as well as other types of infrastructures operating on the same principle of flow (e.g. gas and hydrogen). Hence, the model considers all assets that have a flow usage such as power lines, transformers, breaks, series capacitors and phase shifting transformers.

The main Inputs and Outputs of InfraFair are the following:

Main Inputs:

- Nodal generation injections and withdrawals
- Flows
- Losses
- Length of lines
- Annual cost to be recovered for each line
- Capacity of lines
- Voltage of lines
- Are lines existing or planned? Regional or national?
- Names/IDs or owners of nodes and percentage of ownership

Main Outputs:

- Generation flow contribution: flow on each asset that each generator (or a group of generators) is causing (per snapshot and globally)
- Demand flow contribution: flow on each asset that each demand (or a group of demand) is causing (per snapshot and globally)
- Country flow contribution: flow on each asset that each country (generators and demand) is causing (per snapshot and globally)
- Generation losses contribution: losses on each asset that each generator (or a group of generators) is causing (per snapshot and globally)
- Demand losses contribution: losses on each asset that each demand (or a group of demand) is causing (per snapshot and globally)
- Country losses contribution: losses on each asset that each country (generators and demand) is causing (per snapshot and globally)
- Generator/consumer usage: usage of each asset by each agent (per snapshot and globally)
- Generator/consumer usage fraction: fraction of each asset used by each agent (per snapshot and globally)
- Country usage fraction: fraction of each asset used by each country (per snapshot and global)
- Generation cost contribution: fraction of the cost of each asset that each generator (or a group of generators) is responsible for
- Demand cost contribution: fraction of the cost of each asset that each demand (or a group of demand) is responsible for
- Country cost contribution: fraction of the cost of each asset that each country (generators and demand) is responsible for

- Network user/Country cost: overall cost of the grid of each country that each agent/country is responsible for
- Network user/Country network cost: overall network cost that each agent/country is responsible for
- Country received cost: overall cost of the grid of each country that external agents from each other country are responsible for

2.5 OnSSET

OnSSET is a Geographic Information Systems (GIS) based tool that enhances electrification planning and decision-making for the accomplishment of energy access goals in currently unserved areas. The OnSSET code base is modular and allows the users to specify spatial and temporal resolution of the analysis, GIS input data, technologies and costs. OnSSET is a bottom-up medium- to long-term optimization model that attempts to determine the least-expensive supply option to achieve universal electrification in each site by combining population settlements with various geographical features, socioeconomic data, and demographic information.

The main Inputs and Outputs of InfraFair are the following:

Main Inputs:

- Population:
 - Population size (current and projected for a specific year)
 - Population distribution
 - Ratio of urban population in the selected area in the base year and in the end year
 - Number of people per household in rural/urban areas
 - Administrative boundaries
- Power Grid:
 - Existing HV -High Voltage- network (Optional) : Used to identify and spatially calibrate the currently electrified/non-electrified population.
 - Power Substations (Optional): used to calibrate the currently electrified/non-electrified population and specify grid extension suitability.
 - Planned High Voltage network (including extension to current/future substations, power plants, mines and queries). (Optional)
 - Existing and planned Medium Voltage network (Optional): Used to identify and spatially calibrate the currently electrified/non-electrified population.
 - Grid losses
 - Maximum distance for which the grid can be extended in order to electrify a settlement due to techno-economic considerations. The default value in the model is 50 km.
 - Maximum distance from the existing or planned grid network under which the model will consider a settlement as electrified
 - Maximum distance from the existing or planned road network under which the model will consider a settlement as electrified
- Roads and travel:
 - Current Road infrastructure used to identify and spatially calibrate the currently electrified/non-electrified population. It is also used in order to specify grid extension suitability. (Optional)
 - Travel time: Visualizes spatially the travel time required to reach from any individual cell to the closest town with population more than 50,000 people.
- Electricity demand:

- Custom electricity demand in the end year in each settlement (Optional).
- Annual electricity consumption per household that is expected to be achieved, by the end year
- Ratio between the base and peak load in the selected country
 - Nighttime lights: used to identify and spatially calibrate the currently electrified/non-electrified population.
 - Global Horizontal Irradiation (used to identify availability/suitability of photovoltaic systems):
 - Wind speed: used to identify the availability/suitability of wind power (using Capacity factors).
 - Hydro power potential (Optional): mini/small hydropower potential, incl. environmental, social and topological restrictions
 - Elevation Map
 - Land Cover
 - Service transformers (Optional): used to identify and spatially calibrate the currently electrified/non-electrified population.
 - Costs and prices:
 - Capital costs per technologies: stand-alone diesel generator, stand-alone PV module, mini-grid diesel generator, mini-grid PV system, mini-grid wind powered system, mini grid hydropower system
 - Incremental cost increase for extension of the grid from an electrified settlement to an un-electrified one. Default value set at 10%.
 - Discount rate applied to different technology configuration choices throughout the period of analysis
 - Diesel price (low/high)
 - Grid Price, i.e., cost of generating electricity based on the technologies mix
 - Capital cost of additional grid capacity investment
 - Incremental cost increase for extension of the grid from an electrified settlement to an un-electrified one
 - Electrification rate in the selected area in the base year: What ratio of population is electrified
 - Minimum population value under which the model will consider a settlement as electrified

Main Outputs:

- Population served by each technology in the end year Sectoral Demands
- Number of newly electrified population by each technology in the end year
- Additional capacity required by each technology to fully cover the demand in the end year
- Investment required by each technology to reach the electrification target in the end year
- Generation mix as calculated by the OnSSET analysis
- Lowest LCoE achieved in each location as calculated by the OnSSET analysis

2.6 EV-PV

The main goal of EV-PV is to support planning and decision-making for the deployment of charging stations for electric vehicles (EVs). The EV-PV model is a set of geospatial data layers and calculation modules implemented in the open source *Citiwatts* platform (<https://citiwatts.net/>). This tool, developed as part of the ERANET OpenGIS4ET project, is a GIS (Geographic Information System) tool for territorial energy planning. It is based on the previously developed *Hotmaps* platform. Technological scope: for the time being, the EV-PV model focuses on passenger cars, as this is the main mode of road passenger transport in Europe.

- Geographic scope: the model can be applied to any geographic area, provided the data for this is available. The resolution of geospatial layers can go down to the hectare level.
- Temporal scope: the model mainly focuses on values defined on a daily basis.

⚠ About the EV-PV model in the African context

The EV-PV model is expected to evolve quite significantly based on the available data and the specific needs of the African context. Whether in terms of scope, methodology or inputs/outputs, further investigation and model development is required before arriving at the final model description. Therefore, we only provide a very general description here.

Figure 1 depicts a simplified version of the inputs and outputs of the EV-PV model.

Figure 1: Simplified schematic representation of the inputs and outputs of the EV-PV model

3 Models extensions

In this chapter we describe the models' extensions which are necessary to adapt the models to the African context.

3.1 GENeSYS-MOD – OpenTEPES - Plan4res common extensions

The extensions and adaptations to be carried out for these 3 models are common to all of them. Thus, they are jointly discussed for these three models.

For all 3 models, no extension related to the mathematical modelling nor solving algorithm is required to be able to conduct the 2 case studies foreseen in openMod4Africa. The main necessary changes/extensions in the models are related to the demand (which sectors to be included) side and to the network modelling. The technologies included may also be extended. None of the required extension necessitates adaptation of the model source code, but these extensions will require extension of the technological scope of the model, which mainly means evolutions of the data workflow.

3.1.1 Demand

The energy demand for the European case includes the following components, themselves separated per sectors

- Heat Demand, decomposed in demand for Residential, commercial, industrial uses
- Mobility demand, decomposed in Passenger and Freight demand
- Power demand (excluding demand for heat and mobility)

Cooling demand may also be accounted for.

On the other hand, in the case of Africa, we have identified the following specific demand components that should be explicitly represented:

- Cooking demand: this demand sector is going to evolve in the coming years, with e.g. transition from traditional biomass (wood) cooking to e.g. electric devices.
- Cooling demand may see important increases, in particular in the industry

Additional sectors may also need to be represented in detail, such as Agriculture, regarding the power demand, given increases of pumping needs for agriculture (water supply in fields pumped from water reservoirs) , but this will be evaluated during the case study analyses.

However, adding different components/sectors to the representation of energy demand does not require extensions to any of the models. Nevertheless, it requires adaptations of the data workflows and treatments.

Thus, for example, within openTEPES, the demand of electricity for cooking, for industrial cooling, or for certain agriculture uses, could be represented in two different ways, both just involving a preprocessing of input data:

- One first option would involve representing the demand associated with each of these specific uses of electricity within a separate, virtual, node connected to the electrical node of the grid within the same location. The connection of each of these virtual nodes to the corresponding node of the electric grid is to be represented by means of a line of high capacity that would not be constraining the flow of energy between the two.
- As an alternative, the demand for electricity associated with each of these uses could be represented as heat demand, just with the aim of representing it separately from the demand associated with other electricity uses. Then, together with these virtual heat demands, we should represent heat generators, using electricity to produce the corresponding amount of heat, and heat grids connecting heat demands to heat generators.

3.1.2 Generation/storage

The list and characteristics of generation and storage technologies included in the 3 models is modular and can be adapted by modifying the data. Thus, no modelling extensions are needed in the models to represent these technologies.

3.1.3 Networks

While the European power system is strongly interconnected, with all the users connected to the main grid, this is not the case in Africa. A high share of the population still does not have access to electricity, and rural areas are usually not connected to the grid. The off-grid demand is expected to grow from 6TWh in 2021 to 563TWh in 2040, according to the Continental Power System Masterplan. This means that accounting for the off-grid demand is of paramount importance.

It is of high importance to include, within the OpenMod4Africa studies to be conducted, some accounting for off-grid demand as well as grid integration. Explicitly representing the process of providing additional energy consumers access to electricity, and deploying some grid solutions for them, is possible with the OnSSET model, which is already included in the project Toolbox. However, the 3 models that were originally part of the Toolbox, GENeSYS-MOD, openTEPES, and Plan4RES, can also be used to explicitly represent off-grid demand. This is discussed next:

- GENeSYS-MOD is capable of representing off-grid demand and production as a standalone node, isolated from the surrounding network. However, the model's true strength lies in its ability to simulate a fully integrated energy system, facilitating decarbonization and sector coupling through interactions between multiple interconnected nodes. It can model an off-grid area composed of several nodes, functioning as its own energy system. Additionally, GENeSYS-MOD can assess the effects of connecting such an area to the main grid—either by introducing a new node or increasing demand in an existing one—on the overall energy system. openTEPES can be used to represent off-grid demand, generation, and storage within a separate grid not connected to the main one. All these off-grid distributed energy resources (DERs), which should have been defined making use of other models, like OnSSET, should be represented in an aggregate manner within this separate grid. The electrical size of the virtual grid where off-grid DERs are represented (size meaning the amount of demand and generation within each of the two grids) should not be disproportionately large/small compared to that of the main electrical grid, so as to avoid that the quality of the solution computed for the smaller grid worsens significantly.

- openTEPES can also be used to represent DERs connected to minigrids directly connected to the main one. All those DERs located within minigrids in an area associated with a certain node of the main electrical grid should be represented in an aggregate manner within a virtual node connected to the aforementioned node of the main grid through a line whose capacity should be determined to represent the constraints affecting the flow of energy between the minigrids in this area and the main grid.
- Thus, both in the case of minigrids and offgrid solutions, DERs in them could be represented within openTEPES cases by means of a preprocessing of input data to this tool.
- Plan4res includes a modular modelling of the network, which is described as a series of interconnected nodes, each node being linked to electricity demand timeseries scenarios. The off-grid demand is to be included as specific nodes, with a 0-capacity interconnection with the rest of the system. The plan4res capacity expansion tool optimizes the electricity system capacities accounting for generation, storage and interconnections. This tool may be fed with options computed by OnSSET (and further upscaled) in order to evaluate scenarios with/without connection to the main grid of the system in rural areas. This extension is mainly based on input data preprocessing and should mainly necessitate an extension of the preprocessing tools.
- Adapting the models within the Toolbox to represent cases featuring OnGrid/Offgrid demand and accounting for interconnection options of rural areas should not entail modifying the current models. It would just require implementing some extensions of the pre/post processing tools and data workflows.

3.1.4 Geographic scope

All these 3 models were developed for Europe. Nevertheless, GENeSYS-MOD and openTEPES have already been used in case studies focused on other regions. The 3 models share the same modularity regarding their geographic scope, which is defined via the input data and parameters. This geographic scope can range from a region (a number of interconnected countries, such as e.g. The WAPP or the EAPP region), to a country or subcountry scope, while the geographic resolution can also be adapted to the users needs, e.g. country or subcountry. The main impact on the performance of all the 3 models may be on the size of the resulting optimization problem to solve and, then, on the feasibility for each model to solve this problem, given the IT characteristics of the system on which the model is ran (we could run out of memory), or on the computation time.

3.1.5 Temporal scope

The 3 models are also highly modular in the time dimension and can adapt to address analyses concerning various temporal scopes. GENeSYS-MOD and openTEPES are pluriannual models, while plan4res is mainly designed to run for 1 or 2 years (even though it is possible to run it on a multiyear period, but this may lead to very high computation times).

The temporal granularity of all 3 models is also highly modular, being largely limited by the availability of data (there is no use to run a model with a 5 minute resolution if data are only available with an hourly resolution)

3.2 InfraFair

This model has been developed and used within an African context and thus does not require adaptations. The new version of the model has been extended to allocate, not only the flow on the network, but also the energy losses in the network, to national systems, or even to individual network users. For this, it is essential to record (for each operational snapshot) the power injections and withdrawals at each node and the energy flow and losses on each network asset.

3.3 OnSSET

This model has been developed and used within an African context and, thus, does not require adaptations to deal with the specificities of the African context.

3.4 EV-PV

3.4.1 Introduction

The EV-PV model is a set of geospatial data layers and calculation modules, available online through an open-source Geographic Information System (GIS) platform designed for territorial energy planning (see Deliverable D4.1). The model primarily encompasses three key features:

- High-Resolution geospatial mapping of the charging demand: This feature focuses on passenger transport (cars) and provides detailed spatial resolution.
- Implications of various charging scenarios: This includes analyses of additional load curve and the necessary charging infrastructure to meet the charging demand.
- Assessment of EV-PV coupling benefits: Evaluates the potential advantages and opportunities presented by integrating electric vehicles (EV) with locally installed photovoltaic (PV) systems.

However, the current model is based on assumptions valid within the European context. Therefore, it requires several adaptations to be applicable to the African context and the case studies of the project. Initial investigations and discussions with project partners have highlighted particularities that the model must address. The primary differences are:

- Distinct mobility landscape:
 1. Diverse vehicles and transport modes: For instance, informal public transport systems (paratransit), are highly developed in Africa but are absent in Europe
 2. High spatial variability: Significant differences exist between countries and within countries, particularly between rural and urban areas.
- **Data scarcity:** Accurate and up-to-date data on vehicle usage and mobility habits (e.g., daily distance traveled) are often difficult to obtain.
- **Rapidly changing and unpredictable context:** The dynamic nature of the African context necessitates adaptable and flexible modeling.

The adaptations to address these differences are detailed below in terms of scope, methodology, and inputs/outputs. Please note that these may still evolve based on data availability and feedback from partners during the development process.

3.4.2 Scope

3.4.2.1 Technological Scope

Transport Modes:

The major extension of the EV-PV model is in considering more passenger transport modes beyond privately-owned cars. We plan to include both private and public transport modes:

- Private transport: Cars (already included), motorbikes.
- Public transport: Minibus taxis (informal transport), regular buses, bus rapid transit (BRT).

PV Potential:

The current methodology for estimating PV potential needs to be reviewed. Here, we plan to integrate a model capable of predicting PV potential in more configurations (rooftop PV, utility PV, etc.) based on user input. This will also benefit other models in the project that rely extensively on PV potential.

3.4.2.2 Geographic Scope

As urban areas are likely to hold most of the electric vehicles, the main focus will be on urban areas.

3.4.2.3 Temporal Scope

No changes.

3.4.3 Methodology

The methodology will be adapted to handle the different transport modes:

- **For private mobility:** The main adaptation involves handling intra-urban mobility, which is not precisely accounted for in the current tool. Additionally, we aim to assess expected mobility behavior endogenously to overcome data gaps. For motorbikes, we will also investigate battery swapping as a charging method.
- **For public mobility:** A new methodology is under development for buses and minibus taxis, based on readily available public transport data. The methodology for the BRT is yet to be determined.

The EV-PV model will be divided into several sub-models, each addressing a specific transport mode. If possible, these sub-models will be fully integrated as calculation modules in the online GIS platform. However, we also plan to provide them as standalone Python models for advanced users or if a full integration in the online tool proves challenging.

Economic and environmental impacts of electrification will also be assessed, focusing on fuel cost savings for EV owners and reductions in CO₂ emissions.

To manage uncertainties, efforts will be made to adopt a scenario-based approach when data is unavailable. This will also help to understand the implications of significant potential changes in local contexts. Finally, we will work on coupling the transport modes to inform about multimodal electric transport systems, which is a crucial topic for urban transport planning.

3.4.4 Inputs and Outputs

Input Data:

No major changes are expected for private mobility input data. The model will offer more default values when specific data is not available. For public transport (minibuses and buses), General Transit Feed Specification (GTFS) data will be used, which is generally readily available. Information on vehicle fleet characteristics, particularly electricity consumption per kilometer, will also be required.

Output Data:

No major changes are expected regarding the main outputs of the model.

4 IT perspectives

4.1 Models installation and uses

The first try-ons of models by all the partners allowed the modelling teams to get very useful feedback about the usability of the models by 'external' teams. From this feedback, we can propose the following recommendations for the models, and the Scenario explorer.

4.1.1 Scenario Explorer

Initial interactions with the Scenario Explorer required some explanations and discussion. In particular, the concept of a project template, which is a list of allowed values for, mainly, regions and variables, was important to communicate.

Here it proved useful to motivate the use of such a seemingly restrictive list with the goal of a modeling exercise, which is the comparison between models. Comparison requires a common language aka. project template.

Such a project template is expected to evolve over the course of a project. For OpenMod4Africa, the latest version of the template can be obtained here:

<https://files.ece.iiasa.ac.at/openmod4africa/openmod4africa-template.xlsx>.

Model registration and, associated with it, region aggregation was also covered in the project workshop in Madrid. However, since there are only dummy data sets so far, this process was discussed more in a conceptual way.

4.1.2 GENeSYS-MOD

GENeSYS-MOD installation proved in general quite simple and efficient. Regarding the use of GENeSYS-MOD, the following topics could be enhanced:

- Installation: the tutorial for installation is focused on installing Windows. It should be extended with at least a Linux section (which should be extremely simple as the first trials for installing on Linux were very easy to conduct and proved efficient).
- Excel input datasets: the data format is lacking documentation to deeply understand what each value means. Variable names could be clarified. Each variable should be linked to a variable name in the nomenclature (at least the relation with a variable in the nomenclature); Each value should also be associated with a unit (if not in the excel sheet, then in a documentation file, which should be easily accessible).
- Linkage scripts: A linkage script to convert GENE SYS-MOD results to the IAMC format exists. Nevertheless, this script should allow to convert all GENE SYS-MOD data with the same level of detail as available in the model (e.g. the script today carries out first some technology or sectors aggregations, making it difficult to reuse those data). Moreover, the linkage script should also allow to convert all input data in IAMC format, so as to simplify the workflow involving this and other models.

4.1.3 openTEPES

The following topics related to the use of openTEPES could be enhanced:

- Installation: the tutorial for installation of this tool is focused on installing it on a Windows operating system. The process of installing openTEPES on a Linux environment should also be described within a separate section.
- Input datasets: the input datasets to be fed into this tool should be processed, as described in section 3.1, to represent separately the demand associated with specific uses of electricity of relevance in the African context, as well as DERs within minigrids connected to the main grid, and those making off-grid solutions.
- Linkage scripts: A linkage script to convert openTEPES results to the IAMC data format already exists. However, linkage scripts need to be developed to produce input datasets for openTEPES out of the IAMC datasets produced by GENE SYS-MOD and data from other sources that are also required.

4.1.4 plan4res

The following topics should be enhanced:

- Installation: Installing plan4res is quite complex and requires following a number of different steps. In a further version, the installation procedure will be simplified and will necessitate only 3 main steps: 1- clone from a github repository (which will in one command create the whole platform including the launching and python scripts); 2- run the p4r-env environment to download the sif image, edit the config file to prevent further downloads, and; 3- install sms++.
- Solvers dependence: SMS++ can be used with different solvers: CPLEX, Gurobi, Scip and Highs. We will include the possibility of choosing the solver in a further release. Note that CPLEX and Gurobi are commercial solvers which may require buying a license.
- Windows installation. The current solution relies on the use of the virtual machine software Vagrant. We plan to test the use of WSL, which may be more efficient.

- Linkage scripts: 2 linkage scripts are available: one creates plan4res input datasets out of IAMC data from GENeSYS-MOD, and one converts plan4res outputs to the IAMC format. No extension is planned.

4.2 OM4A workflow

Figure 2 shows an example of what could be a workflow among the three models originally integrated into the Toolbox. The steps of it are listed next:

1. Step 1: Input datasets are created for GENeSYS-MOD,
2. Step 2: GENeSYS-MOD is run and results are produced.
3. Step 3: Inputs and outputs of GENeSYS-MOD (at least the variables which are either worth publishing or will be used as inputs by another model) are converted to the IAMC format using linkage scripts.
4. Step 4: A selection of those IAMC data is uploaded to the scenario explorer while all IAMC data are stored on a local data storage (which can be the own disk of the team conducting the case study with the workflow or any tool meant for exchanging data)
5. Step 5: The IAMC data produced in step 3 and locally stored in step 4 is converted to plan4res data format using plan4res linkage scripts. Additional data for plan4res are created.
6. Step 6: plan4res is run and results are produced.
7. Step 7: Inputs and Outputs of plan4res (at least the variables which are either worth publishing or will be used as inputs by another model) are converted to the IAMC format using linkage scripts.
8. Step 8: A selection of those IAMC data is uploaded to the scenario explorer while all IAMC data are stored on a local data storage (which can be the own disk of the team conducting the case study with the workflow or any tool meant for exchanging data)
9. Step 9: The IAMC data produced in steps 3 and 7 and locally stored in steps 4 and 8 is converted to openTEPES data format using openTEPES linkage scripts. Additional data for openTEPES are created.
10. Step 10 : openTEPES is run and results are produced.
11. Step 11: Inputs and Outputs of openTEPES (at least the variables which are either worth publishing or will be used as inputs by another model) are converted to the IAMC format using linkage scripts.
12. Step 12: A selection of those IAMC data is uploaded to the scenario explorer while all IAMC data are stored on a local data storage (which can be the own disk of the team conducting the case study with the workflow or any tool meant for exchanging data)

Figure 2: Example of workflow

This example only includes the 3 models GENesYS-MOD, openTEPES and plan4res, but it could be extended with the other models. OnSSET in particular will be run independently but its outputs shall be used as inputs by plan4res and openTEPES (after upscaling). A linkage script will also be necessary to connect these models. The EV-PV model, also independent of the three aforementioned models, will be used in a second phase to conduct local analyses of transport electrification informed by the core models' outputs. Data will be accessible via the GIS tool hosting the EV-PV model (no linkage scripts required). On the other hand, inputs for InfraFair are dependent on the outputs of openTEPES. The relevant input and output data are converted using linkage scripts from and to the IAMC format.

4.2.1 Linkage scripts

As seen above, each model will be connected to the OM4A platform via linkage scripts. A linkage script allows to translate each model's own dataformat to/from the IAMC format. Having all the data within the IAMC format will allow:

- Upload to the scenario explorer,
- Validation of the data (a validation function is available in pyam as well as in the scenario explorer, which guarantees that all data are using only valid variables and regions)
- Exchange of datasets among models
- Easy visualization of the data by the OM4A geographic visualization function
- Easy publishing of data and results via upload to the public version of the scenario explorer.

4.2.2 Data storage

The Scenario Explorer has been created for external sharing of data. It cannot be used as an exchange tool in a data workflow. We then recommend that each case study team uses its own means of exchanging data (on a hard disk if using the same server, via any secured data exchange means). Nevertheless, exchanged data between teams/models should as much as possible be limited to IAMC format (<https://docs.ece.iiasa.ac.at/iamc.html>) csv or Excel files.

In addition to adhering to a common data format, it is advised to use the openmod4africa workflow repository on GitHub (<https://github.com/iiasa/openmod4africa-workflow>) together with the nomenclature package (<https://nomenclature-iamc.readthedocs.io/en/stable/>) to ensure that the data exchanged is compliant with the project template.

4.2.3 Visualisation tool

The visualization tool should be useable both via its connection to the scenario explorer or by directly 'feeding' it with IAMC format csv files.

5 Conclusion

The models functionalities have been analysed in regard to the openMod4Africa case studies specifications. The main conclusions regarding extension needs are the following::

- The mathematical modelling is sufficient to represent the required characteristics of the African energy systems. Thus, no extension to this mathematical modelling, nor the linked solving algorithm, is necessary.
- 2 models will not require any extensions:
 - **InfraFair** (used to determine the network utilisation by agents-(demand and generators using the network- and countries) has been developed and used within an African context and, thus, do not require adaptation.
 - **OnSSEt** (Geographic Information Systems (GIS) based tool that enhances electrification planning and decision-making for the accomplishment of energy access goals in currently unserved areas) has also been developed and used within an African context and, thus, do not require adaptation.
- 3 models will not require extensions regarding the mathematical formulation nor solving algorithm. However, the technological scope of the models needs to be extended regarding the demand side (to include different demand sectors, in particular cooking) as well as for the network modelling (to include the offgrid demand). These extensions will be conducted via evolutions of the data workflow:
 - **GENESYS-MOD** (which is the model used to analyze long-term low-carbon energy transition pathways considering all energy sectors: electricity, buildings, industry, and transport)
 - **openTEPES** (decision support system for defining the integrated generation, storage, and transmission expansion plan of a large-scale electric systems)

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- **plan4res** (power system model, which includes capacity expansion module (adaptation of the generation and storage mix as well as of the existing interconnections of a given year), focused on the optimization of the strategies for managing seasonal storages, and the simulation of the system operation.)
 - 1 model will require a few extensions to be implemented:
 - **EV-PV** (planning and decision-making for the deployment of charging stations for electric vehicles) Including more passenger transport modes (Private transport: add motorbikes, public transport: minibus taxi, regular buses, rapid transit buses) will see its methodology applied to determine the PV potential will be adapted to the local context.

For all models, a documentation (regarding installation and use) will be issued, and linkage scripts will be implemented (or extended when existing as for GENeSYS-MOD, plan4res and openTEPES), as to allow a smooth workflow between the models in the case studies.

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